

HYDROMAGNETIC NON-DARCY CONVECTIVE HEAT TRANSFER FLOW OF EG-BASED $MoS_2 - SiO_2$ NANO FLUIDS IN CYLINDRICAL ANNULUS WITH HEAT SOURCES AND ACTIVATION ENERGY : A FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH

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Abstract

Exploring nanofluids offers a promising avenue for enhancing various functionalities essential for efficient heat exchange. These advancements hold significant potential to benefit industries such as pharmaceutical manufacturing, microelectronics, engine cooling systems, and household refrigeration. This study examines the magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) non-Darcy convective heat transfer flow of ethylene glycol (Eg)-based $MoS_2 - SiO_2$ nanofluid within a cylindrical annulus, incorporating the effects of activation energy. The nonlinear coupled governing equations are solved using the Galerkin finite element method with quadratic approximation functions. The analysis emphasizes the influence of key parameters on engineering variables and the distribution of fluid velocity (u), temperature (θ), and nanoparticle concentration (C). Furthermore, the Nusselt number (Nu) and Sherwood number (Sh) are numerically evaluated along the cylinder boundaries. Findings indicate that increasing activation energy (E_1) and temperature difference ratio (δ_1) lead to a reduction in velocity and temperature while enhancing nanoparticle concentration within the flow region. Additionally, an increase in space-dependent heat source (A_{11}), temperature-dependent heat source (B_{11}), activation energy (E_1), and temperature difference ratio (δ_1) results in a rise in Sh for Eg- MoS_2 nanofluid, while leading to a decrease in Eg- SiO_2 nanofluid on the outer cylinder at $\eta = 2$.

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1. Introduction

To achieve significant cost and energy savings, it is essential to enhance heat transfer mechanisms. With rapid advancements in science and technology, there is an increasing demand for compact devices that offer high efficiency, precise operation, and long-term reliability. As a result, researchers are actively seeking to optimize heat transfer processes, particularly in applications where thermal management is critical. Traditional fluids such as water, oil, kerosene, and ethylene glycol often exhibit inadequate heat transfer properties, prompting the development of nanofluids

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as a viable alternative. The appearance of nanofluids comes from the investigative work conducted by Choi and Eastman [10]; Buongiorno[9]. Their exploration unveiled the superior heat transfer capabilities of nanofluids when compared to traditional convective fluids. Nano-enhanced fluids showcase a diverse range of applications across different industries such as the automotive sector, electronics field, aerospace realm, machining, solar energy, and even the field of biomedicine. Further investigation by Eastman et al. [14] disclosed the measurement of thermal conductivity of $C_2H_6O_2$ (ethylene glycol) fluid with Cu-nanofluids. Sheikholeslami and Ganji [29] studied the doings of shape factor on forced convective flow of nanofluid with Lorentz forces. Investigation of using multi-layer PCMs in the tubular heat exchanger with periodic heat transfer boundary condition was analysed by Sadeghi et al. [17]. Their results assert that unlike the outer section, the inner one is more susceptible to the change of hot heat transfer fluid (HHTF) temperature. Some researchers examined nanofluids under numerous features in the refs. (Yin et al. [36]; Zhang et al. [37]).

Magneto hydrodynamics (MHD) involves the manipulation of magnetic force that influences the movement of a conductive fluid, inducing currents that result in a counteracting Lorentz force within the field. The impact of magnetism on nanofluids or combinations like hybrid nanofluids presents a myriad of practical uses, such as miniature MHD pumps, bearings, flow gauges, MHD power generators, and regulating the flow of liquid metal substances. Recently, Siva Shankara Rao [30] has demonstrated the combined effects of thermal radiation, dissipation, thermos-diffusion, and variable viscosity on the MHD convective heat transfer flow of $MoS_2 - SiO_2$ nanofluids in a cylindrical annular region. Subsequently, several authors (Refs: [3, 11, 23, 31–33]) have investigated the influence of variable viscosity, heat flux, and thermal conductivity on the heat transfer characteristics of CuO -water, Al_2O_3 -water, and TiO_2 -water nanofluids. Their studies focused on heat transfer over a stretching sheet in a porous medium, along with the enhancement of natural convection-driven hydrodynamic flow in a cylindrical annulus.

Darcy's law is a fundamental principle that describes the relationship between pressure drop and velocity in fluid flow through porous media. It was originally formulated by Henry Darcy based on experiments involving water movement through sand beds. This law is widely applied in analysing water flow through aquifers, as well as tracking the movement of gas, water, and oil within oilfield reservoirs. However, Darcy's linear model becomes inadequate when dealing with higher flow rates, as it does not account for inertial effects. To address this limitation, an additional term, known as the Forchheimer correction, is introduced. Forchheimer [16] conducted studies on fluid flow in porous media under high-velocity conditions and observed that as the flow rate increased, inertial forces started to significantly influence the movement of the fluid. To incorporate these effects, he suggested modifying Darcy's equation by adding a term representing the kinetic energy of the fluid. Among the various extensions of Darcy's law, the Darcy-Forchheimer model is one of the most widely used for describing nonlinear flow behaviour in porous media.

Over time, researchers such as Wooding [35] and Brinkman [7, 8] have further refined Darcy's formulation to provide a more accurate representation of convective flow in porous structures.

Examining the effects of heat generation or absorption is crucial when studying fluids involved in endothermic or exothermic chemical reactions. This phenomenon plays a key role in applications such as semiconductor wafers and electronic chips. Alam and Ahammad [4] employed the Nachtsheim-Swigert shooting iteration method combined with a sixth-order Runge-Kutta integration scheme to analyse heat and mass fluxes, considering the influence of Dufour and Soret effects. Their study assumed that electrical conductivity varies with velocity and found that increasing the order of chemical reaction enhances velocity and concentration profiles while reducing temperature profiles. Additionally, Kumar et al. [21] investigated magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) free convective flow over a vertical cone with variable electrical conductivity in the presence of a chemical reaction, utilizing an efficient Crank-Nicolson-type finite difference method. Doganchi et al. [13] explored the magneto-hydrodynamic fluid squeezed between two parallel disks by considering Joule heating, thermal radiation, and adding different nanoparticles. Their findings include that the fluid velocity increases while the temperature profile decreases with increasing suction parameter.

In the fields of chemistry and physics, activation energy is defined as the minimum energy required for a chemical reaction to occur. It is typically measured in joules per mole (J/mole), kilojoules per mole (kJ/mole), or kilocalories per mole. Activation energy represents the potential energy barrier that must be overcome to transition between the initial and final thermodynamic states. For a reaction to proceed efficiently, the temperature must be sufficiently high to ensure that a considerable number of molecules possess translational energy equal to or exceeding the activation energy. The concept of activation energy was first introduced in 1889 by the Swedish physicist Svante Arrhenius [34]. Several researchers have explored the effects of activation energy in fluid dynamics and heat transfer. Abu Nada et al. [1] and Abu-Nada [2] studied the natural convection of nanofluids in a concentric annulus, considering variations in viscosity and thermal conductivity. Amitosh Tiwari et al. [6] analysed how activation energy influences magneto hydrodynamic (MHD) heat transfer in nanofluids flowing over a vertical wavy surface with changing properties. Kathyani and Subramanyam [18] examined the role of activation energy in thermally radiative, electrically conducting viscous fluid flow within a vertical channel under the influence of heat sources. Additionally, researchers such as Satya Narayana and Ramakrishna [27], Nagasasikala [24], and Devasena [12] have investigated the impact of activation energy on fluid flow behaviour. More recently, Lalramngaihuali and Prasada Rao [22] conducted a numerical study on MHD convective heat transfer involving ethylene glycol-based single-walled (SWCNT) and multi-walled (MWCNT) carbon nanotube nanofluids in a cylindrical annulus, considering the effects of variable viscosity and activation energy. Kiran Kumar et al. [20] explored the impact of thermal radiation on non-Darcy hydro magnetic convective heat and mass transfer in a cylindrical annulus,

focusing on water-based SWCNT and MWCNT nanofluids with thermo-diffusion and chemical reaction effects. Effect of thermophoresis particle deposition in free convection boundary layer from a vertical flat plate embedded in a porous medium was scrutinized by Chamka et al. [5].

This study examines the behaviour of a $MoS_2/SiO_2 - EG$ nanofluid within a cylindrical annulus, particularly under the influence of a spatially varying heat source or sink. Molybdenum disulphide (MoS_2), an inorganic compound classified as a metal dichalcogenide, consists of alternating molybdenum and sulphur layers. It naturally occurs as molybdenite, a black-silver crystalline mineral. Its high thermal stability and low interfacial energy make it an effective stabilizing agent in nanofluids. Silicon dioxide (SiO_2), on the other hand, has a higher electronegativity compared to molybdenum, which inhibits sulfatase production in contrast to MoS_2 . Considering these material characteristics, the focus of our research is on the flow dynamics of an incompressible, laminar ethylene glycol-based nanofluid containing MoS_2 and SiO_2 particles within a cylindrical annular geometry.

1.1. Applications Transport phenomena influenced by both thermal and concentration buoyancy play a crucial role in various engineering systems and natural environments. These processes are widely utilized in industries such as chemical distillation, heat exchangers, solar energy collection, and thermal protection systems, where the driving force arises from the combined effects of heat and chemical reactions. In atmospheric flows, sunlight-induced thermal convection is influenced by variations in water vapour concentration. Similarly, buoyancy-driven convection resulting from coupled heat and mass transfer in porous media has significant applications in energy-related engineering. These include moisture migration, fibrous insulation, chemical pollutant dispersion in saturated soils, geothermal energy extraction, and underground disposal of hazardous waste. The present study on flow and heat transfer between concentric cylinders is particularly relevant to nuclear waste disposal research. It has been established that radioactive waste can be securely stored underground to minimize exposure to human populations. The scientific and industrial advancements in fluid flow and heat transfer within cylindrical structures have further underscored their importance. Applications range from optical fibre coating, nanowire fabrication, and cancer treatment to metal spinning and various other industrial manufacturing processes. Figure 1(a) showcases different industrial uses of nanofluids.

1.2. Novelty The novelty of this study lies in the exploration of the magneto-radiative EG based nanofluids flow in the concentric annulus considering viscous dissipation, thermal radiation, Joule heating, radiation absorption, thermos-diffusion, activation energy, non-Darcy and non-uniform heat source/sink on convective heat and mass transfer flow.

2. Formulation of the Problem

This study investigates the mixed convective flow of MoS_2 and SiO_2 nanofluids through a porous medium within a vertical circular annulus, where constant concentration and heat are maintained. To account for density variations limited to

(a) Applications of nanofluids

(b) Configuration of the problem

FIGURE 1

thermal and molecular buoyancy forces, the Boussinesq approximation is applied. The Brinkman-Forchheimer-Extended Darcy model, which incorporates the effects of inertia and surface interactions, is utilized to describe the momentum equation in the porous region. The governing equations are nonlinear and coupled, while the fluid flow is unidirectional along the axial path of the cylindrical annulus. (Figure. 1(b)).

The following assumptions are supported the flow problem.

- The flow is laminar and steady.
- Applying the Boussinesq approximation to account for density variations limited to thermal and molecular buoyancy forces.
- Assuming magnetic Reynolds number is small, the induced magnetic field is neglected in comparison to applied magnetic field.
- Walls of the cylinders are coated with porous medium and the distance between them is $b - a$. At $r = a$ the inner cylinder is held at temperature T_i , concentration C_i , while at outer cylinder positioned at $r = b$ temperature is maintained at T_o and concentration is maintained at C_o .
- The flow direction is vertical upward driven. (Z-axis).
- EG based MoS_2 and SiO_2 nanofluids are taken in the annular region.
- Assuming the cylinders are infinitely long, the flow and thermal fluids are considered to be fully developed.
- Non-uniform heat source/sink constraints are incorporated into the energy

equation.

- The viscous and Joule heating effects are taken into account.
- The impact of Darcy- Forchheimer phenomena is also considered for the flow system.
- It is assured that the base fluid (ethylene glycol) and suspended nanoparticles (MoS_2 and SiO_2) are in thermal equilibrium.

2.1. Governing equations By using the above assumptions, the governing equations are

$$-\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}\delta_1 r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\mu_{nf}(T)r \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right) - \left(\frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}k} \right) u - \frac{\sigma_{nf}\mu_e^2 H_o^2}{\rho_{nf}r^2} - \frac{\delta_1 F}{\rho_{nf}\sqrt{k}} u^2 + (\rho\beta)_{nf}(T - T_o) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} u \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = k_{nf} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + q''' - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(rq_r)}{\partial r} + \mu_{nf} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right)^2 + (\sigma_{nf}\mu_e^2 H_o^2)(u^2) + Q'_1(C - C_0) \quad (2.2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = D_B \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) - k_c C + \frac{D_m K_T}{T_s} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) - k_c (C - C_0) \left(\frac{T}{T_0} \right)^n \exp \left(\frac{-E_a}{KT} \right) \quad (2.3)$$

where u, θ, C are axial velocity, temperature and concentration respectively. and k =porous medium, k_f = thermal diffusivity, F =Reynolds number, the microstructure of the porous medium and D_B = molecular diffusivity, D_m = mass diffusivity, K_T =diffusion ratio, β =thermal expansion, q_r =radiation absorption, C_p =specific heat, ρ =density, g =gravity, ρ_{nf} = density of nanofluid. μ_{nf} =dynamic viscosity of nanofluid, k_{nf} =thermal conductivity of nanofluid.

2.2. Boundary conditions The relevant boundary conditions for the problem under consideration are as follows:

$$u = 0, T = T_i, C = C_i \quad \text{on} \quad r = a; \quad u = 0, T = T_o, C = C_o \quad \text{on} \quad r = a + s \quad (2.4)$$

The coefficient q''' is the rate of internal heat generation (> 0) or absorption(< 0). The internal heat generation /absorption q''' is modelled as (Emad and Abo-Eldahab et al.[15]) as

$$q''' = \left(\frac{k_f}{a^2 \nu} \right) (A^*(T_w - T_o)u + B^*(T - T_o)) \quad (2.5)$$

Where A^* and B^* are coefficients of space dependent and temperature dependent internal heat generation or absorption respectively. It is noted that the case $A^* > 0$ and $B^* > 0$, corresponds to internal heat generation and that $A^* < 0$ and $B^* < 0$, the case corresponds to internal heat absorption case.

In the presence of radial magnetic field, the velocity depends only on the radial coordinate and all the other parameters except θ, C and pressure are functions of r and z , z being the vertical co-ordinate. We take $\frac{dT}{dz} = A$, $\frac{dC}{dz} = B$ where A and B are temperature and concentration gradients respectively.

Suitable non-dimensional variables are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \eta^* &= \frac{r}{a}, & z^* &= \frac{z}{a}, & s^* &= \frac{s}{a}, \\ p^* &= \frac{pa^2\delta_1}{\rho\nu_f^2}, & \pi &= \frac{dp^*}{dz}, & u^* &= \left(\frac{\nu_f}{a}\right)u, \\ \theta &= \frac{T - T_o}{T_i - T_o}, & C^* &= \frac{C - C_o}{C_i - C_o} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.6)$$

2.3. Thermophysical properties The thermal and physical properties of nanoparticles when combined with ethylene glycol as the primary medium are presented in Table 1.

The properties of nanofluids, including density, heat capacity, thermal expansion rate, electrical and thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity and viscosity, are described as follow:

Density: The effective density of the nanofluid is given by

$$\rho_{nf} = (1 - \phi)\rho_f + \phi\rho_s \quad (2.7)$$

Where ϕ is the solid volume fraction of nanoparticles. Heat capacity: The heat capacitance of the nanofluid is obtained as

$$(\rho C_p)_{nf} = (1 - \phi)(\rho C_p)_f + \phi(\rho C_p)_s \quad (2.8)$$

Thermal expansion coefficient: The thermal expansion coefficient of nanofluid can determine by

$$(\rho\beta)_{nf} = (1 - \phi)(\rho\beta)_f + \phi(\rho\beta)_s \quad (2.9)$$

Electrical conductivity: Electrical conductivity of nanofluid is given by

$$\sigma_{nf} = \sigma_f \left(1 + \frac{3(\sigma - 1)\phi}{\sigma + 2 - (\sigma - 1)\phi} \right), \quad \sigma = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f} \quad (2.10)$$

Thermal conductivity: The thermal conductivity of the nanofluid is determined as

$$\frac{k_{nf}}{k_f} = \frac{(k_s + 2k_f) - 2\phi(k_f - k_s)}{(k_s + 2k_f) + \phi(k_f - k_s)} \quad (2.11)$$

Thermal diffusivity: The thermal diffusivity of the nanofluid is obtained by

$$\alpha_{nf} = \frac{k_{nf}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} \quad (2.12)$$

Viscosity: The dynamic viscosity of nanofluid is set by

$$\mu_{nf} = \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi)^{2.5}} \quad (2.13)$$

The underscores nf , f , and s indicate thermophysical factors of the nanofluid, base liquid, and nanosolid particles respectively, whereas ϕ represents the solid volume fraction of the nanoparticles. The thermophysical properties of the nanofluids are given in Table 1 (See Oztop and Abu-Nada [25]).

TABLE 1: Physical properties of fluid phase (Ethylene Glycol) and nanoparticles

Physical properties	Fluid phase (Ethylene Glycol)	MoS ₂	SiO ₂
C_p (J/kg·K)	2430	397.21	703
ρ (kg/m ³)	1115	5060	2200
k (W/m·K)	0.253	904.4	1.2
$\beta \times 10^{-5}$ (1/K)	99	2.8424	0.056
σ	0.05	10 ⁶	10 ⁷

The resulting non-dimensional form as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \eta} - B \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \eta} \right) &= A_1 A_3 \pi e^{B\theta} + \delta_1 A_1 \left(D^{-1} + \frac{A_6 M^2 e^{B\theta}}{\eta^2} \right) u \\ &+ \delta_1^2 A_1 (D^{-1})^{1/2} \Delta u^2 - \delta_1 A_1 A_4 G e^{B\theta} \theta \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(A_5 + \frac{4Rd}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right) &+ (A_{11} u + B_{11} \theta) + E_c P_r (e^{-B\theta}) \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial \eta} \right)^2 \\ &+ M^2 E_c P_r (u^2) + Q_1 C = A_3 P_r N_1 u \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\partial C}{\partial \eta} \right) - \gamma C &= S c N_2 u + S c S_0 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial \eta^2} + \frac{1}{\eta} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \eta} \right) \\ &- \gamma C (1 + n \delta_1 \theta) \exp \left(-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta \theta} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

Where $B = m(T_o - T_i)$ (Viscosity parameter), $\Delta = FD^{-1/2}$ (Forchheimer number), $G = \frac{g\beta(T_o - T_i)a^3}{\nu^2}$ (Grashof number), $M^2 = \frac{\sigma \mu_c^2 H_o^2}{av}$ (Magnetic parameter), $D^{-1} = \frac{a^2}{k}$ (Inverse Darcy parameter), $P_r = \frac{\mu C_p}{k_f}$ (Prandtl number), $R_d = \frac{4\sigma^* T_o^3}{k_f \beta_R a}$ (Thermal Radiation parameter), $E_c = \frac{\nu_f}{a^2 C_p (T_i - T_o)}$ (Eckert number), $S_c = \frac{\nu}{D_B}$ (Schmidt number), $\gamma = \frac{k_c a^2}{D_B}$ (Chemical Reaction parameter), $S_o = \frac{D_m K_T (T_o - T_i)}{T_s (C_o - C_i)}$ (Soret parameter), $Q_1 = \frac{Q'_1 (C_w - C_o)}{a^2 (T_w - T_o)}$ (Radiation absorption parameter), $\theta_w = \frac{T}{T_o}$, $\delta_1 = \theta_w - 1$ (Temperature difference ratio), $E_1 = \frac{E_a}{KT_o}$ (Activation energy parameter), $A_{11} = \frac{A^*}{AvF}$ (Space dependent heat source), $B_{11} = \frac{B^*}{A^2 \nu F}$ (Temperature dependent heat source), and $N_1 = \frac{A}{a\Delta T}$, $N_2 = \frac{B}{a\Delta C}$, $A_1 = \frac{1}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}}$, $A_2 = (1-\phi) + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right)$, $A_3 = (1-\phi) + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho C_p)_s}{(\rho C_p)_f} \right)$, $A_4 = (1-\phi) + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho\beta)_s}{(\rho\beta)_f} \right)$, $A_5 = \frac{k_{nf}}{k_f}$, $A_6 = 1 + \frac{3(\sigma-1)}{\sigma+2-(\sigma-1)\phi}$, $\sigma_{nf} = \sigma_f A_6$, $\sigma = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_f}$

The corresponding non-dimensional conditions are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u = 0, \quad \theta = 1, \quad C = 1 \quad \text{on } \eta = 1 \\ u = 0, \quad \theta = 0, \quad C = 0 \quad \text{on } \eta = 1 + s \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.17)$$

3. Finite Element Analysis

The study of finite elements with nonlinear quadratic estimate factors is performed over the radial distance across the circular duct. The behaviour of the u , θ and C profiles are being digitally investigated for various modifications in governing parameters. The Galerkin approach was used in the variational formulation of each element to create global linked indices for u , θ and C during the finite element analysis. Choose an arbitrary element e_k and let u^k, θ^k and C^k be the values of u , θ and C in the element e_k as residuals.

$$E_u^k = \frac{d}{d\eta} \left(\eta \frac{du^k}{d\eta} \right) - B \left(\frac{du^k}{d\eta} \right) \left(\frac{d\theta^k}{d\eta} \right) + \delta_1 A_1 A_4 \eta G e^{B\theta^k} (\theta^k) - \delta_1 A_1 \left(D^{-1} + \frac{A_6 M^2 e^{B\theta^k}}{\eta^2} \right) \eta u^k - A_1 \delta_1^2 \Delta \eta (u^k)^2 - A_1 A_3 e^{B\theta^k} \quad (3.1)$$

$$E_\theta^k = \frac{1}{P_r} \left(A_5 + \frac{4R_d}{3} \right) \frac{d}{d\eta} \left(\eta \frac{d\theta^k}{d\eta} \right) - A_5 P_r N_1 u^k + (A_{11} u^k + B_{11} \theta^k) + Q_1 C^k \quad (3.2)$$

$$E_c^k = \frac{d}{d\eta} \left(\eta \frac{dC^k}{d\eta} \right) - S_c N_2 u^k - \gamma C^k + S_c S_o \frac{d}{d\eta} \left(\eta \frac{d\theta^k}{d\eta} \right) - \gamma C^k (1 + n\delta_1 \theta^k) \exp \left(-\frac{E_1}{1 + \delta_1 \theta^k} \right) \quad (3.3)$$

where u^k , θ^k and C^k are values of u , θ and C in the arbitrary element e_k . These are expressed as linear combinations in terms of respective local nodal values.

$u^k = u_1^k \psi_1^k + u_2^k \psi_2^k + u_3^k \psi_3^k$, $\theta^k = \theta_1^k \psi_1^k + \theta_2^k \psi_2^k + \theta_3^k \psi_3^k$, $C^k = C_1^k \psi_1^k + C_2^k \psi_2^k + C_3^k \psi_3^k$ where $\psi_1^k, \psi_2^k, \psi_3^k$, etc. are Lagrange's quadratic polynomials.

Galerkin's method is used to convert the partial differential equations 3.1–3.3 into matrix form, resulting in 3×3 local stiffness matrices. All these local matrices are assembled into a global matrix by substituting the global nodal values and using inter-element continuity and equilibrium conditions. The resulting global matrices are solved by an iterative procedure until convergence. i.e., $|u_{i+1} - u_i| < 10^{-6}$ is obtained.

4. Engineering quantities

The skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number are key variables that can be effectively represented using mathematical expressions.

The τ (Skin friction) is determined using the given formula $\tau = \left(\frac{du}{d\eta} \right)_{\eta=1,1+s}$.

The rate of heat transfer (Nu) is calculated using the corresponding formula

$$Nu = - \left(\frac{d\theta}{d\eta} \right)_{\eta=1,1+s}$$

The rate of mass transfer (Sh) is obtained through the specified formula

$$Sh = - \left(\frac{dC}{d\eta} \right)_{\eta=1,1+s}$$

5. Results validation

To ensure the reliability of our research, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of the Nusselt and Sherwood numbers across various parameters, validating our findings against the work of Siva Shankara Rao [30]. This evaluation was performed by setting all other variables in the simulation to zero (i.e., $E_1 = \delta_1 = \Delta = A_{11} = B_{11} = 0$) as outlined in Table 2. A comparison of the results in Table 2 and 3 demonstrate a strong agreement between our outcomes and those reported by Siva Shankara Rao [30], confirming the accuracy and credibility of our study.

TABLE 2: Numerical comparison of results for different parameters

Parameter	Value	MoS ₂ – Ethylene Glycol				SiO ₂ – Ethylene Glycol			
		Siva Shankar Rao [30]		Present Values		Siva Shankar Rao [30]		Present Values	
		Nu(1)	Sh(1)	Nu(1)	Sh(1)	Nu(1)	Sh(1)	Nu(1)	Sh(1)
Rd	2.5	1.000001	2.39337	1.001542	2.39315	0.98671	3.95291	0.98675	3.95289
	4.5	0.999997	2.38798	0.999984	2.38091	1.00016	5.40498	1.00014	5.40499
	6.5	0.999988	2.38098	0.999937	2.38032	1.00099	6.54383	1.00082	6.54387
Ec	2.1	1.000001	2.39337	1.001542	2.39315	1.00262	3.95362	1.00264	3.95364
	4.1	0.999988	2.38598	0.999983	2.38092	1.00293	5.40478	1.00291	5.40477
	6.1	0.999782	2.38099	0.999821	2.38087	1.00369	6.54301	1.00464	6.54314
B	0.2	1.000001	2.39337	1.001542	2.39315	0.99635	3.95412	0.99633	3.95413
	0.4	0.999995	2.37997	0.999999	2.37996	0.99756	5.40521	0.99755	5.41731
	0.6	0.999993	2.37883	0.999982	2.37881	0.99942	6.54302	0.99904	6.54313
Pr	0.71	1.000001	2.39337	1.000154	2.39315	1.00374	3.95322	1.00367	3.95327
	1.71	0.999996	2.38598	0.999984	2.38088	0.99786	5.40541	0.99787	5.40543
	3.71	0.999984	2.38099	0.999979	2.38082	0.90691	6.54588	0.90689	6.54582

TABLE 3: Numerical comparison of Nusselt number (Nu) results for different Prandtl numbers

Prandtl Number (Pr)	Shaiq et al. [28]	Salawu et al.[26]	Khan et al.[19]	Siva Shankar Rao [30]	Present Values
0.07	0.0656	0.0656	0.0673	0.0686	0.0685
0.20	0.1691	0.1691	0.1678	0.1702	0.1744
0.70	0.4539	0.4539	0.4549	0.4602	0.4627
2.00	0.9114	0.9114	0.9109	0.9115	0.9123
7.00	1.8854	1.8854	1.8894	1.8902	1.8958
20.00	3.3539	3.3539	3.3537	3.3542	3.3541

6. Results and Discussion

The impact of various parameters on velocity (u), temperature (θ) and nanoconcentration (C) have been illustrated in figures. 2(a)–2(c), 3(a)–3(c), 4(a)–4(c), 5(a)–5(c), 6(a)–6(c), 7(a)–7(c), 8(a)–8(c), 9(a)–9(c), 10(a)–10(c), 11(a)–11(c), 12(a)–12(c), 13(a)–13(c). The parameter values adapted for this investigation include: $G = 2$, $M = 0.5$, $K = 0.01$, $R_d = 2.5$, $E_c = 2.5$, $A_{11} = 0.1$, $B_{11} = 0.5$, $B = 0.2$, $E_1 = 0.3$, $F = 0.1$, $\delta_1 = 0.1$, $\Delta = 0.1$

6.1. Analysis of the fluid velocity The Velocity upsurges with rising in Grashof number (G)/ Magnetic parameter (M)/ Forchheimer parameter (Δ) in both nanofluids (Figs.2(a),3(a) and 12(a)) while in case of increase in Porous permeability (K)/ dissipative energy (E_c)/ space dependent heat source (A_{11})/ viscosity parameter (B)/ activation energy (E_1)/ Prandtl number (P_r)/ temperature difference ratio (δ_1) it decreases in both nanofluids (figs.4(a),6(a),7(a),9(a),10(a),11(a) and 13(a)). The growth in $G/M/\Delta$ increases the width of momentum boundary layer in both nanofluids but the thickness of this boundary layer decays with the rising values of $K/E_c/A_{11}/B/E_1/P_r/\delta_1$ in both nanofluids. The velocity decays in EG based MoS_2 nanofluid but it rises in EG based SiO_2 nanofluid with an enhancement in thermal radiation (R_d)/ heat generating source (B_{11}) (figs.5(a),8(a)). In this case momentum boundary layer becomes thinner in EG based MoS_2 nanofluid while it becomes thicker in later nanofluid.

6.2. Analysis of the fluid temperature It is identified that temperature (θ) decreases with rising values of Grashof number (G) but it increases with the enhancement in the values of Magnetic parameter (M)/ thermal radiation (R_d)/ heat generating source (B_{11})/ Prandtl number (P_r) in both nanofluids (figs.2(b), 3(b),5(b),8(b) and 11(b)). This can be attributed to the fact that thermal boundary layer becomes thinner with the enhancement in G while it becomes thicker with rising in the values of $M/R_d/B_{11}/P_r$ in both nanofluids. Increasing the values of dissipative energy (E_c)/ space dependent heat source (A_{11})/ viscosity parameter (B)/ activation energy (E_1)/ Forchheimer parameter (Δ)/ temperature difference ratio (δ_1) augments the temperature in EG based MoS_2 nanofluid but decays it in EG based SiO_2 nanofluid (figs.6(b), 7(b),9(b),10(b),12(b) and 13(b)). This is due to the fact that width of the thermal boundary layer becomes large in EG based MoS_2 but it becomes smaller in EG based SiO_2 for the growing values of $E_c/A_{11}/B/E_1/\Delta$. It is observed that in the presence of heat generating source (B_{11}) heat is generated in the boundary layer which results in an enhancement in temperature in both nanofluids.

6.3. Analysis of the fluid concentration It is noted that nanoconcentration (C) decays with the growing values of Grashof number (G)/ Magnetic parameter (M)/ heat generating source (B_{11}) in both nanofluids (figs. 2(c),3(c), and 8(c)) while in case of increasing values of porous permeability (K)/ thermal radiation (R_d)/ dissipative energy (E_c)/ space dependent heat source (A_{11})/ viscosity parameter (B)/ activation energy (E_1)/ Prandtl number (P_r)/ Forchheimer parameter (Δ)/ temperature difference ratio (δ_1) nanoconcentration increases in EG based MoS_2 nanofluid but it decreases in later nanofluid (figs.4(c),5(c),6(c),7(c),9(c),10(c),11(c),12(c) and 13(c)). This is due to the fact that solutal boundary layer becomes thinner with the enhancement in the values of $G/M/B_{11}$ in both nanofluids. For the expanding values of $K/R_d/E_c/A_{11}/B/E_1/P_r/\Delta/\delta_1$ solutal boundary layer thickness becomes larger in EG based MoS_2 but it becomes smaller in EG based SiO_2 .

The values of u , θ , and C in Eg-based MoS_2 nanofluid are relatively greater than those in Eg-based SiO_2 nanofluid with the upscaling values of $G/E_c/A_{11}/P_r/\delta_1$. The values of C in Eg-based MoS_2 nanofluid are relatively greater than those in Eg-based SiO_2 nanofluid, while the values of u and θ in Eg-based SiO_2 nanofluid

are higher than those in Eg-based MoS_2 nanofluid with the increasing values of $M/K/R_d/B_{11}/B/E_1/\Delta$.

6.4. Skin friction, Nusselt number and Sherwood number analysis It is noticed that Sherwood number (Sh) increases in both types of nanofluids with a growth in Grashof number (G)/ temperature difference ratio (δ_1) while the rate of mass transfer (Sh) decays in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid and enhances in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid with the rising values of $M/K/R_d/E_c/A_{11}/B_{11}/B/E_1/\Delta/P_r$ at $\eta = 1$. It is noted that an increment in increases Sherwood number (Sh) in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid while decreases Sherwood number in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid at $\eta = 2$ (Tables 4 and 5).

The values of skin friction (τ) and Sherwood number (Sh) in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid are relatively greater than those in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid while the values of Nusselt number (Nu) in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid are relatively lesser than those in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid for the variations in at an inner cylinder. The values of skin friction (τ) and Nusselt number (Nu) in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid are relatively higher than those in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid while the values of Sherwood number in Eg based SiO_2 nanofluid are relatively larger than those in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid for the variations of the same parameters $G/M/K/R_d/E_c/A_{11}/B_{11}/B/E_1/\delta_1/\Delta/P_r$ at the outer cylinder (Tables 4 and 5).

FIGURE 2: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with G

7. Conclusions

The effect of activation energy, variable viscosity on MHD convective heat transfer flow of Eg based MoS_2 and SiO_2 nanofluids through a porous medium in a vertical channel have been analysed by executing the governing equations numerically. The findings of this analysis are:

- Increase in Gashof number (G) increases velocity and reduces temperature and nanoconcentration in both nanofluids. Higher the Lorentz force/Lesser the porous permeability(K) smaller the velocity, nano-concentration and larger the temperature.

FIGURE 3: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with M

FIGURE 4: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with K

FIGURE 5: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with R_d

FIGURE 6: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with E_c

FIGURE 7: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with A_{11}

FIGURE 8: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with B_{11}

FIGURE 9: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with B

FIGURE 10: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with E_1

FIGURE 11: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with P_r

FIGURE 12: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with Δ

FIGURE 13: Variation of [a] Velocity (u), [b] Temperature (θ), [c] Nano-Concentration (C) with δ_1

- Increase in $R_d/E_c/A_{11}$ decays the velocity and grows the temperature and nanoconcentration in both nanofluids.
- Increase in Viscosity parameter(B)/activation energy(E_1) temperature difference ratio(δ_1) decays velocity, enhances temperature and concentration in the flow region.
- The influence of inertia and boundary effects is to enhance velocity, temperature and nanoconcentration in nanofluids.
- The skin friction(τ) decays with increase in $G/M/K/R_d/B_{11}/\Delta/P_r$ and opposite effect is noticed in the case of $E_c/A_{11}/B/E_1/\delta_1$ at the outer cylinder($\eta = 2$) in both nanofluids.
- Rate of heat transfer enhances in Eg based MoS_2 nanofluid and decays in Eg- SiO_2 nanofluid with increase in $G/M/K/R_d/E_c/A_{11}/E_1/\Delta$.
- Increase in $G/M/K/R_d/E_c/A_{11}/B_{11}/B/P_r/\Delta/\delta_1$ increases Sh in Eg- MoS_2 nanofluid and decreases in Eg- SiO_2 nanofluid at $\eta = 2$.

TABLE 4: Skin friction (τ), Nusselt number (Nu), and Sherwood number (Sh) with MoS_2 & $SiO_2 - Ethylene Glycol$ (Eg) at $\eta = 1$

Parameter	Value	$MoS_2 - Ethylene Glycol$			$SiO_2 - Ethylene Glycol$		
		$\tau(1)$	Nu(1)	Sh(1)	$\tau(1)$	Nu(1)	Sh(1)
G	2	-0.496599	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466525	0.99962	3.95412
	5	-0.391422	0.99999	2.38253	-0.293798	1.00216	5.40598
	10	-0.201074	0.99921	2.38012	-0.060138	1.00343	6.54497
M	0.5	-0.496599	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466525	0.99962	3.95412
	1.0	-0.502152	0.99995	2.38106	-0.463261	0.99988	5.40544
	1.5	-0.516481	0.99994	2.38017	-0.457929	0.99994	6.54382
K	0.01	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99962	3.95412
	0.04	-0.505636	0.99996	2.38098	-0.466538	1.00008	5.40534
	0.08	-0.505639	0.99995	2.38058	-0.466525	1.00012	6.54357
R_d	2.5	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466638	0.99867	3.95291
	4.5	-0.505652	0.99999	2.38098	-0.466577	1.00016	5.40498
	6.5	-0.505672	0.99998	2.38038	-0.466532	1.00042	6.54383
E_c	2.1	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466571	1.00262	3.95362
	4.1	-0.505652	0.99988	2.38098	-0.466575	1.00293	5.40478
	6.1	-0.505672	0.99979	2.38029	-0.466585	1.00319	6.54301
A_{11}	0.1	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99965	3.95412
	0.3	-0.505652	0.99997	2.38098	-0.466556	1.00032	5.40527
	0.5	-0.505672	0.99982	2.38029	-0.466583	1.00045	6.54509
B_{11}	0.5	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99963	3.95412
	0.75	-0.505652	0.99991	2.38098	-0.466538	0.99780	5.40588
	0.95	-0.505672	0.99985	2.38028	-0.466512	0.99579	6.54459
B	0.2	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99963	3.95412
	0.4	-0.580189	0.99995	2.37997	-0.534495	0.99975	5.40588
	0.6	-0.667539	0.99993	2.37883	-0.614054	0.99985	6.54302
E_1	0.2	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99963	3.95412
	0.4	-0.505652	0.99996	2.26273	-0.466552	1.00004	4.98414
	0.6	-0.505672	0.99995	2.15999	-0.466559	1.00012	5.55557
P_r	0.71	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466592	1.00374	3.95322
	1.71	-0.505652	0.99996	2.38098	-0.466549	0.99978	5.40541
	3.71	-0.505672	0.99984	2.38029	-0.466451	0.99069	6.54588
Δ	0.1	-0.496623	1.00001	2.39337	-0.466547	0.99963	3.95412
	0.3	-0.351570	0.99867	2.38309	-0.234892	1.00284	5.40621
	0.5	-0.198614	0.99762	2.38017	-0.049569	1.00353	6.54495
δ_1	0.2	-0.496623	1.00000	2.39332	-0.466547	0.99963	3.95412
	0.4	-0.505652	0.99996	2.39667	-0.466554	1.00021	5.46361
	0.6	-0.505672	0.99995	2.40905	-0.466555	1.00043	6.67142

TABLE 5: Skin friction (τ), Nusselt number (Nu), and Sherwood number (Sh) with MoS₂ & SiO₂ – Ethylene Glycol (Eg) at $\eta = 2$

Parameter	Value	MoS ₂ – Ethylene Glycol			SiO ₂ – Ethylene Glycol		
		$\tau(2)$	Nu(2)	Sh(2)	$\tau(2)$	Nu(2)	Sh(2)
G	2	0.497433	0.99995	0.439836	0.472184	0.99652	0.235403
	5	0.437923	0.99992	0.443829	0.393495	0.99444	0.119759
	10	0.351067	0.99989	0.445242	0.262445	0.99318	0.066827
M	0.5	0.497433	0.99995	0.439836	0.472184	0.99652	0.235403
	1.0	0.486862	0.99997	0.444731	0.469174	0.99643	0.120494
	1.5	0.481676	0.99999	0.444848	0.459251	0.99501	0.068587
K	0.1	0.497409	0.99993	0.439836	0.472159	0.99652	0.235403
	0.4	0.490032	0.99994	0.444782	0.472178	0.99623	0.120542
	0.8	0.490018	0.99995	0.444789	0.472192	0.99549	0.068683
R_d	0.5	0.497409	0.99993	0.439836	0.472254	0.98659	0.236066
	1.5	0.490016	0.99997	0.444782	0.472197	0.99350	0.120696
	5.0	0.490008	0.99998	0.444789	0.472141	0.99659	0.068591
E_c	0.2	0.497409	0.99999	0.439836	0.472185	0.99313	0.235553
	0.4	0.490016	1.00001	0.444781	0.472183	0.99302	0.120661
	0.6	0.490006	1.00003	0.444786	0.472178	0.99244	0.068766
A_{11}	0.1	0.497409	0.99999	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.3	0.490016	1.00002	0.444782	0.472166	0.99899	0.120568
	0.5	0.490001	1.00003	0.444792	0.472203	1.00217	0.068428
B_{11}	0.5	0.497409	0.99999	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.7	0.490016	0.99997	0.444781	0.472146	0.99738	0.120438
	0.9	0.490012	0.99984	0.444798	0.472132	0.99858	0.068549
B	0.2	0.497409	0.99993	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.4	0.523934	0.99996	0.445402	0.504108	0.99685	0.120871
	0.6	0.561474	0.99998	0.446097	0.539428	0.99769	0.069283
E_1	0.2	0.497409	0.99994	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.4	0.490016	0.99996	0.465642	0.472163	0.99625	0.148971
	0.6	0.490013	0.99999	0.484143	0.472169	0.99557	0.114965
P_r	0.71	0.497409	0.99981	0.439836	0.472198	0.99219	0.235686
	1.71	0.490016	0.99994	0.444782	0.472167	0.99661	0.120525
	3.71	0.490009	1.00014	0.444791	0.472075	1.00732	0.068319
Δ	0.1	0.497409	0.99993	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.3	0.418862	0.99991	0.443485	0.365936	0.99385	0.119486
	0.5	0.348579	0.99995	0.444203	0.261049	0.99315	0.066826
δ_1	0.2	0.497409	0.99992	0.439836	0.472159	0.99653	0.235403
	0.4	0.490016	0.99994	0.442709	0.472164	0.99616	0.118032
	0.6	0.490009	0.99995	0.443001	0.472169	0.99543	0.065419

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